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Effects of meteorological factors on students' commute to high school

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ABSTRACT

Limited physical activity and a sedentary lifestyle are common among young people. The use of a bike sharing system (BSS) to commute to and from school seems to be a good way of promoting physical activity among students. However, choosing a means of transportation may be influenced by meteorological conditions. This study aimed to determine how meteorological conditions affect students' use of BSS for commuting to and from high school. A self-organizing maps analysis was conducted to obtain information on the characteristics of the students' daily commute. Use of the BSS and the meteorological condition of each day were selected as input variables. The Kruskal–Wallis test was used to determine the main effect of the cluster on the input variables. The results revealed six clusters (profiles) of days. Four clusters represented favorable meteorological conditions and higher BSS use. The remaining clusters grouped unfavorable conditions and lower BSS use. Comfortable temperatures (14.4–22.6 °C), low humidity, and light-to-moderate breeze (i.e. wind) had a positive influence on the use of the BSS by the students. Conversely, temperatures <14.2 °C and high humidity (>73 %) had a negative effect on the use of the BSS. Furthermore, rainfall had a nonlinear effect on the use of the BSS, whereas heavy precipitation had a negative effect on use of the BSS. However, light precipitation had no effect on BSS use. These findings indicate that meteorological conditions have a significant effect on the use of a BSS for active commuting to school by young students. Efforts should be made to provide better BSS infrastructure to encourage young people to use the BSS for active commuting.

1. Introduction

Insufficient physical activity and a sedentary lifestyle have become common among young people worldwide (Marshall et al., 2004; Tremblay et al., 2011). This has led to an increase in the incidence of health problems such as obesity and the risk of mortality among young people (Engeland et al., 2003). To combat this problem, the World Health Organization recommends that children and adolescents engage in a minimum of one hour of moderate-to-vigorous intensity physical activity daily (World Health Organization, 2010). Encouraging active transportation, such as walking or cycling, is one way to reduce sedentary time and achieve physical activity recommendations among young people (Prince et al., 2022).

The bicycle-sharing system (BSS) has gained popularity as form of active transportation. It is generally considered a safer mode of transport than regular cycling (Martin et al., 2016) and provides an

environmentally friendly alternative to traditional urban transport (Chiariotti et al., 2018). This sustainable form of transportation offers benefits when connected to public transit, reduces reliance on private vehicles, and promotes a healthy lifestyle (Davison et al., 2008; Pérez et al., 2017). Use of active transportation in younger populations, particularly adolescents, is low (Carver et al., 2011). A review identified distance between home and school as the main barrier to active commuting (Davison et al., 2008), with long distances limiting walking in particular. The BSS can be an interesting alternative means of transportation to and from school (Fulton et al., 2005; Schofield et al., 2020) and a simple method of increasing physical activity (Davison et al., 2008). Moreover, it has been observed that students inhale more polluted air when walking to school in urban areas than when cycling. This is due to increased exposure to air pollution while walking long distances (Gao et al., 2022). Therefore, different projects have been established to promote the use of the BSS as a key mode of transportation

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and a means of improving the health of young people (Dietz et al., 2019; D'Orso, et al., 2019).

Several studies have analyzed factors such as city infrastructure (D'Orso, et al., 2019), socioeconomic status (Molina-García and Queralt, 2017), high school typology, and proximity to public transportation (e. g., bus) (Rodríguez and Vogt, 2009) to identify the factors that affect students' choice of using a BSS for active commuting to school. Meteorological conditions are key factors that affects the use of the BSS (Eren and Uz, 2020; Fishman et al., 2015); however, their impact on BSS use among students has not been studied extensively. In the general population, moderate-to-warm temperatures are favorable for BSS use, whereas very warm and cold temperatures are unfavorable (Eren and Uz, 2020; Gebhart and Noland, 2014). However, there is no consensus among studies on which temperatures are associated with increased or decreased BSS use. Eren and Uz (2020) conducted a review of factors that affect BSS demand and concluded that the optimal temperature range for BSS use is between 20 °C and 30 °C. However, recent studies revealed that the optimal temperatures for BSS use in New York and San Francisco are above 30 °C and below 20 °C, respectively (Ahn et al., 2022).

The results of studies on the effects of other meteorological factors, such as precipitation, humidity (Eren and Uz, 2020; Gebhart and Noland, 2014; Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023; Ashqar et al., 2019), wind (Fishman et al., 2015; Böcker et al., 2019; Helbich et al., 2014), and atmospheric pressure (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023; Chibwe et al., 2021; Pazdan et al., 2021), on BSS use are inconsistent. Some studies indicated that precipitation reduces the use of BSS as a form of active transportation (Rixey, 2013; Kim, 2018), whereas others found no effect (Ahn et al., 2022; Ashqar et al., 2019). High humidity tends to reduce both the likelihood and duration of cycling trips, especially when combined with elevated temperatures, due to increased thermal discomfort (Ashqar et al., 2019; Monforte and Ragusa, 2022). Wind speed is generally perceived as a barrier to active commuting (Fishman et al., 2015); however, recent studies suggest that its effect depends on its interaction with other weather variables, such as temperature and rainfall (Böcker et al., 2019). Atmospheric pressure has received less attention in the literature and is often found to have limited explanatory power (Chibwe et al., 2021; Pazdan et al., 2021). Nevertheless, a recent study showed that extreme values (either very low or very high) may negatively influence BSS use (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2024). This effect may be due to their physiological effects on fatigue and oxygen uptake (Correa et al., 2015). Although these findings are still preliminary, they suggest that atmospheric pressure may be a more relevant factor for active commuting than previously thought.

One reason for these discrepancies may be the limitations of the linear predictive analyses commonly conducted in these studies. These analyses can produce multicollinearity errors and unstable estimates, leading to inaccurate results with statistically significant differences (Lu et al., 2014). Ahn et al. (2022) noted that the relationship between precipitation and the number of bicycles used is nonlinear. Precipitation does not have a negative effect on BSS use when there is little rain (Ahn et al., 2022); however, it appears to have an effect on BSS use on the rainiest days (Zhu et al., 2020). Notably, the authors could not draw solid conclusions regarding precipitation because of the limited number of rainy days analyzed in their study.

A recent study conducted using self-organizing maps (SOM) analysis demonstrated that nonlinear analyses are suitable for estimating BSS use and its interaction with meteorological variables (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). For instance, temperatures ranging from 19 °C to 25 °C and humidity levels $\leq 65.6\%$ are associated with high BSS usage. However, should the humidity exceed 65.6 %, the maximum tolerable temperature for high BSS usage decreases to 23.5 °C.

Meteorological conditions can affect both the use of BSS and the benefits it provides to young students. However, no study has examined how these conditions affect BSS use among young people for active commuting to and from high school. A recent study emphasized the

importance of comprehensively understanding the impact of meteorological factors on active commuting to school among adolescents (Müller et al., 2020). This is because environmental factors could affect this population differently than they do adults. Furthermore, commuting to work or school is distinctly different from leisure travel, such as shopping, recreational activities, and dining (Li et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022). Understanding the effects of meteorological conditions on commuting is crucial for promoting active transportation among young people. However, active commuting to school has not been thoroughly explored from the perspective of weather conditions. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the use of the BSS by adolescents for active commuting to school using nonlinear analysis, specifically SOM analysis.

Considering the above and given the design and methodology applied in the present study, this work makes a novel contribution by being the first to analyse the influence of meteorological conditions on the use of BSS among adolescents for commuting to high school. Unlike previous research, which has focused predominantly on adult users or on aggregated patterns, our approach targets an understudied population segment. Methodologically, the use of SOM combined with k-means clustering enables the identification of complex and non-linear relationships between weather variables and BSS usage, without imposing pre-defined classification thresholds. These methodological and contextual innovations provide new evidence to inform policies aimed at promoting active commuting in younger populations, even under variable weather conditions.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Data acquisition

This was a cross-sectional study conducted in València (Spain). The characteristics of the city and its BSS have been described previously (Pellicer-Chenoll et al., 2021). Among its characteristics, València is a predominantly flat city, with minimal topographical variation across its urban area. For this reason, elevation was not considered a relevant factor in the present study. This study was conducted using combined data on the movements of all BSS users (independent of age) and daily meteorological conditions from January 1, 2019, to April 30, 2021. On the one hand, the data on users were provided by the local company operating the BSS. These data were previously anonymized and filtered by the company according to the registered users' age, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.

Only adolescents were included in the present study. The period of restricted movement caused by the COVID-19 pandemic were excluded from the analysis. Concretely, from March 15, 2020, to September 7, 2020. Non-school days, such as weekends and the summer period, were also excluded.

From the 276 BSS stations and 103 high schools, only schools with a BSS station located within a 200-meter radius were selected. For this purpose, Q-Geographic Information System 3.22 software (QGIS, GNU – General Public License) was used (Fig. 1A and B). This criterion ensured that the BSS was a viable commuting option for students. As a result, 79 high schools and 78 BSS stations were included (Fig. 1C). From the database provided by the local BSS company, data on the trips of users aged between 14 and 17 years old ($n = 9468$) were selected. Only the trips recorded during the time slots designated for entry and exit into the schools were included in the data matrix. For instance, if a high school entrance time is 8:00 a.m., the time slot between 7:30 a.m. and 8:00 a.m. was chosen. Data on a total of 40125 trips were collected. Subsequently, the total travel time for all the selected trips was calculated for each day to determine the daily time variable for use of the BSS for active commuting to school. On the other hand, data on meteorological variables were obtained from the Open Weather Map Company.

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Valencia [Universitat de València] (code 2451613).

Fig. 1. The geolocation procedure and selection of the BSS sample.

After collecting all relevant information, a data matrix was generated by incorporating data on student trips to and from high school into the BSS and weather factors. Each row of the matrix represents a different day (i.e., case), and each column represents a variable. The variables are as follows:

- Total time: total daily time spent by students using BSS for active commuting to school.
- Temperature: daily average temperature in °C.
- Atmospheric pressure: daily average atmospheric pressure (mb).
- Humidity: daily average relative humidity (%).
- Wind: daily average wind speed (m/s).
- Precipitation: daily average precipitation (l/m2).

2.2. Self-organizing maps analysis

SOM analysis was performed using MATLAB R2022a (Mathworks Inc., Natick, MA, USA) software and the SOM toolbox (version 2.0 beta) for MATLAB (Vesanto et al., 1999). The analysis was performed using daily aggregated data. Each case in the SOM represents one day, with the corresponding values for BSS usage (i.e., total commuting time) and the meteorological variables.

Active commute to school and meteorological features were integrated as input variables in the SOM analysis to establish relationships between them and plot them on maps for improved visualization and interpretation of the results. This technique provides multiple advantages (Herrero-Herrero et al., 2017) and identifies clusters with higher accuracy than regularly used clustering techniques (Melo Riveros et al., 2019).

The SOMs were based on unsupervised artificial neural networks that

classified the days (i.e., the cases in our study) according to their similarities. Specifically, the analysis was performed in three steps (Seifert et al., 2023; Pellicer-Chenoll et al., 2015). First, the network was constructed based on the number of cases included in the dataset (i.e., 395) and the proportions of the two main eigenvalues of the dataset. A network with 13×8 neurons (height \times width) was constructed through this process. Second, the initialization phase was started through randomized and linear initialization. During this procedure, a weight was assigned to each neuron for each input variable. Third, the model was trained to search for the best solution using sequential and batch algorithms (Oliver et al., 2018), which was repeated 100 times to explore all the spaces of possible aggrupation solutions. Thus, the neuronal weights were modified according to the values of the input variables. In practice, each day was mapped to the neuron with the closest weight vector, measured by Euclidean distance. Once a neuron was selected as the ‘winner’ of the day, its value and those of the neighboring neurons were adapted to the input values. Thus, days with similar characteristics were located near the neurons (Estevan et al., 2019). A total of 1600 SOM analyses were performed: 100 repetitions \times 2 initialization methods \times 2 training methods \times 4 neighborhood functions. Finally, by multiplying the quantization and topographical errors, a map with minimum error was obtained (Molina-García et al., 2018). Subsequently, a k-means method was used to classify the neurons into clusters (i.e., profiles) according to their characteristics. This method attempts to minimize the Euclidean difference between the input values of the days and centroids of the clusters (Kohonen et al., 2009). The number of clusters that provide the best solution was established using the Davies-Bouldin index. Finally, the obtained clusters were used to describe the meteorological and BSS usage characteristics of the analyzed days.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Information on the days in each cluster was obtained to calculate the descriptive data for the variables. The effect of the cluster on variables was determined using the Kruskal-Wallis test, and pairwise comparisons were performed using the Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc test. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software, version 28 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Rainy days were counted for each cluster and the percentage was calculated.

3. Results

Descriptive statistics for the 395 days analyzed are presented in Table 1. Valencia has mild winters and warm summers. Minimum temperature is 5.32 °C and maximum temperature of 28.75 °C (excluding July and August, the hottest months). The humidity level is usually high, sometimes exceeding 90 %. According to the Beaufort scale, wind in Valencia is usually a breeze of different intensities and rainfall is infrequent.

The Davies-Bouldin index showed that six clusters were the best classification solution. Each cluster comprised neurons (Fig. 2C), and each neuron contained days (Fig. 2D). Hence, the clusters were comprised of days (Fig. 2B). The input variables with the characteristics of each day categorized according to component maps are shown in Fig. 2A. In these maps, blue neurons indicate low values and yellow

neurons indicate high values. Centrality measures and their dispersion per cluster are shown in Fig. 3. The percentage of days per month was analyzed for each cluster (Fig. 4).

Statistical analysis was performed to determine the principal effect of the cluster on each variable (Table 2). Pairwise comparisons of the clusters for each variable and the descriptive data of the clusters are shown in Table 3. The number of days with precipitation in each cluster was calculated to determine the percentage of rainy days per cluster (Table 4).

To improve the understanding of Table 3 and discussion section, the results for each meteorological variable have been expressed through categorizations. Temperature and humidity have been classified based on a recent study conducted in the same city (València, Spain) (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). Since this is a region with a warm Mediterranean climate, temperatures below 14 °C are considered cold, and temperatures above 19 °C are considered hot. The climate between these ranges is considered comfortable. Humidity is typically considered excessively low when it is below 30–40 % and high when it exceeds 60–70 %, as these levels can have negative health consequences (Guarnieri et al., 2023). Therefore, based on the results of the previous study by Villarrasa-Sapiña and colleagues (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023), this study considers humidity to be low when it is below 40 %, high when it exceeds 65.6 %, and comfortable when it falls within this range of percentages. According to Beaufort Scale, wind can be calm (<0.3 m/s), light (0.3–1.3 m/s), breeze (1.4–2.9 m/s), moderate (3–5.3 m/s), fresh breeze (5.4–10.5 m/s), or strong (>10.5 m/s) (National Weather Service of US, 2024). Finally, based on the (Meet Office, 2012) (United Kingdom’s National Meteorological Service), the precipitation can be light (<0.5 l/m²), moderate (between 0.5 and 4 l/m²), or heavy (>4 l/m²).

4. Discussion

In this study, we conducted a nonlinear analysis to determine the effects of weather conditions on the use of a BSS by adolescents (14 to 17 years of age) for active commuting to school. In the analysis, we classified 395 days into six clusters (profiles) to establish relationships between meteorological factors and the total duration of BSS use by these adolescents. The results revealed a clear difference between these profiles, with four profiles showing high BSS usage and the remaining two showing low BSS usage. Specifically, clusters 1 (C1), 3 (C3), 4 (C4) and 6 (C6) showed significant differences compared to clusters 2 (C2) and 5 (C5). C4 had the highest BSS usage, followed by clusters C3, C6, C1, C5, and C2. The relationships between the variables for each profile are presented in Table 3.

The highest BSS usage was recorded in C4, C3, C6, and C1. C4 had days with comfortable temperatures, lowest atmospheric pressure and humidity (comfortable humidity), highest wind velocity (fresh breeze), and moderate precipitation on days when it rains (43.84 % of the days, Tables 3 and 4). C3 had the highest temperatures (the warmest profile), moderate humidity, intermediate atmospheric pressure, wind velocity, and a few days with some precipitation. C6 had comfortable temperatures and humidity, intermediate atmospheric pressure, and wind velocity, and a few days with light precipitation (cluster with lowest precipitation). Low BSS usage was recorded in C1, which had warm

Table 1
Descriptive data for the input variables.

	Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Interquartile range	Minimum	Maximum
Total time (min)	1041.97	43.03	981	855.21	30	10391
Temperature (°C)	16.09	0.23	15.22	4.54	5.32	28.75
Atmospheric pressure (mb)	1017.13	0.35	1017.04	6.90	993.92	1034
Humidity (%)	64.79	0.67	65.58	13.31	33.71	92.95
Wind (m/s)	3.86	0.09	3.24	1.73	1.65	10.46
Precipitations (l/m ²)	0.10	0.02	0	0.36	0	4.58

Fig. 2. Results of the SOM analysis. Notes: A) Component maps of the input variables, showing a color representation of the values of the days assigned to each neuron, with yellow indicating high values and blue indicating low values. B) Number of days included in each cluster. C) Clusters obtained through K-means clustering. D) Hit map per neuron, illustrating the distribution of days across the map.

temperatures, high humidity (>65.6 %), moderate atmospheric pressure and wind velocity, and many days with precipitation (40.38 % of the days, Table 4). The lowest BSS usage was recorded in C5 and C2. C5 had comfortable temperatures, moderate atmospheric pressure and wind velocity, the highest humidity, consistent moderate precipitation and days with abundant precipitation (RI > 4, see Table 3). C2 had the lowest temperatures, as it is the only cluster with cold temperatures, the highest atmospheric pressure, high humidity (>70 %), the lowest wind velocity (breeze), and some days with precipitation.

These results demonstrate that comfortable temperatures and humidity favorable conditions for BSS use (C4). Additionally, both cool and warm temperatures may be related to high BSS usage if the humidity level is low (C6 and C3, respectively). However, high humidity slightly impairs BSS usage on days with warm temperatures (C1). Furthermore, the results confirmed that cold temperature with high humidity has a negative effect on BSS usage (C2). These results are similar to those

reported recently found by Villarrasa-Sapiña et al. (2023). The humidity level (>70 %) that reduces the time students spend using the BSS for commuting is higher than that for the general population (>65 %) (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). Previous studies have confirmed that high humidity levels negatively affect the use of BSS (Eren and Uz, 2020; Ashqar et al., 2019), indicating that humidity is a crucial factor that affects active transportation in humid regions.

The results of some studies suggest that low temperature has a negative impact on BSS usage regardless of the humidity level. However, València experiences mild winters, and use of the BSS on the coldest days depends on other factors such as humidity or precipitation (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). After conducting this study, we identified days with temperatures below 13 °C and humidity level below 65 % because the clusters obtained did not show a profile with low temperatures and low-to-moderate humidity levels. Only 38 days were identified and they were distributed equally among C2, C4, and C6. Therefore,

Fig. 3. Characteristics of clusters per input variable.

it can be concluded that cooler temperatures alone are not quite relevant in warm climates, such as that of the Mediterranean, if the humidity level is not high. This is because there are only a few annual days with extremely cold temperatures ($<10^{\circ}\text{C}$) in these climates.

The results of this study indicated that both atmospheric pressure and wind velocity seemed not to affect use of the BSS by adolescents. However, a relationship between atmospheric pressure and active commuting to school was observed; the highest atmospheric pressure value was associated with the lowest level of BSS usage (i.e., C2) and vice versa (i.e., C4). However, this result is not consistent because there were other influencing factors in these profiles. This finding is in line with the results of previous studies, which were not consistent enough for a specific conclusion regarding the relationship between atmospheric pressure and BSS usage to be drawn (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023; Chibwe et al., 2021). Wind velocity seemed to show a positive relationship with BSS use, a finding that contradicts those of previous studies (Eren and Uz, 2020), which indicated that wind velocity alone negatively affects BSS use. Recent studies have demonstrated that wind velocity depends on other variables to influence cycling (Böcker et al., 2019; He et al., 2019). This could explain the inconsistent results observed in the present study. However, it is important to note that the wind velocity recorded in this study was not a strong breeze according to the Beaufort scale (C4 had the highest median; 6.4 m/s). This suggests that adolescents living in hot climates may prefer a stronger breeze to alleviate warm temperatures.

Analysis of the precipitation results (Tables 3 and 4) showed how a rainy day can affect BSS use (e.g., C5), especially if the humidity level is high. This finding explains why students prefer non-active transport (Kamargianni and Polydoropoulou, 2013). However, this result was only applicable when precipitation was abundant. This indicates that light precipitation (e.g., C1 and C4) is not a relevant factor that affects BSS use among students (Ahn et al., 2022; Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). These findings underscore the strong nonlinear influence of precipitation, showing substantial declines in cycling rates once rainfall surpasses certain levels. This suggests that policies aiming to promote

cycling should particularly address infrastructure and protective measures to mitigate the deterrent effect of precipitations.

4.1. Policy implications

The means of transport chosen by students for urban trips varies depending on the weather. Negative meteorological conditions, such as abundant precipitation, lead to reduced use of the BSS and increased use of motorized transport (Wadud, 2014). Therefore, estimation of BSS use is vital for the implementation of policies to improve active transportation among young people.

People generally prefer public transport to bicycles (Böcker et al., 2016); however, establishing a sustainable system to ensure that air pollution does not increase excessively (due to the use of private motorized transport) could expand and improve urban school transport services. In addition, the number of green areas should be increased to mitigate excessive heat and humidity (as seen in the days in C1), which appear to slightly reduce BSS use among students. Among the high BSS usage profiles, this cluster had the lowest BSS usage level. Expanding green spaces could also help prevent potential health risks associated with such meteorological conditions in adolescents (Gutiérrez et al., 2021).

Students should be encouraged to use the BSS for active commuting to school on days with favorable weather conditions; however, this requires the development of more infrastructure. Specifically, as only 28.26 % of the BSS stations in Valencia are located near schools, the city needs more BSS stations near high schools to encourage the use of the service by students. Moreover, most high schools have only one BSS station, and some even share the same BSS station. This results in some students choosing not to use the BSS due to a lack of availability or parking spaces (Estevan et al., 2018). Therefore, adding more BSS infrastructure near high schools to promote this mode of transport will be beneficial.

Additionally, the results highlight the existence of specific usage patterns, such as the one observed in C4, which concentrates the highest

Fig. 4. Annual distribution of the days with characteristics of each cluster.

Table 2
Effect of the cluster on dependent variables.

Variables	H ₅	p-Value
Total time (min)	33.89	< 0.001
Temperature (°C)	247.92	< 0.001
Atmospheric pressure (mb)	242.82	< 0.001
Humidity (%)	292.45	< 0.001
Wind (m/s)	218.59	< 0.001
Precipitations (l/m ²)	105.15	< 0.001

levels of BSS use among adolescents under favorable weather conditions. These peak usage profiles can serve as a reference for the design and timing of promotional campaigns or educational programs aimed at encouraging active commuting. Aligning such initiatives with periods of higher natural demand may improve their effectiveness and long-term adoption.

4.2. Limitations and future research

The present study is, to our knowledge, the first to apply SOM analysis to evaluate the effects of meteorological conditions on BSS use among adolescents, addressing limitations of traditional approaches.

However, several limitations should be noted. First, the study focuses solely on València, a city with a specific climate, so the findings may not be directly generalisable to other locations with different climates or cycling cultures. Second, we did not examine school infrastructure or surrounding urban features, which could influence BSS use under varying weather conditions. Third, the analysis relies on aggregated meteorological and usage data, which may mask individual variability in commuting behaviour. Finally, other potential determinants of active commuting (such as socio-economic status, built environment, or parental attitudes) were not included and warrant exploration in future research.

5. Conclusions

This is the first study to demonstrate the direct effects of meteorological factors on use of the BSS for active commuting to school. In this study, the interaction of the variables in a warm Mediterranean climate was analyzed using nonlinear relationships. The results showed that the days with the highest BSS usage for active commuting to school were characterized by temperatures between 14.4 °C and 22.6 °C, low relative humidity, light-to-moderate wind velocity (between 3 m/s and 6.4 m/s), and light precipitation. Notably, the maximum temperature was approximately 21.6 °C when the humidity level was high. In contrast,

Table 3
Comparisons of variables between clusters.

	Total time	Temperature	Atmospheric pressure	Humidity	Wind	Precipitations
Cluster 1 (n = 52)	1070.5 ^{C2,C5} [2849]	21.68 ^{C2,C4,C5,C6} [10.8]	1016.85 ^{C2,C4,C5,C6} [15.58]	72.71 ^{C3,C4,C5,C6} [28.17]	3.13 ^{C2,C4} [4.59]	0 ^{C2,C3,C5,C6} [1.34]
Cluster 2 (n = 98)	738.5 ^{C1,C3,C4,C6} [2853]	12.68 ^{C1,C3,C4,C6} [12.07]	1024.58* [18]	73.04 ^{C3,C4,C5,C6} [33.42]	2.60* [3.51]	0 ^{C1,C4,C5} [0.85]
Cluster 3 (n = 52)	1161 ^{C2,C5} [10310]	22.66 ^{C2,C4,C5,C6} [10.57]	1015.38 ^{C2,C4,C6} [18.92]	56.02 ^{C1,C2,C5} [31.46]	3.56 ^{C2,C4,C5} [3.24]	0 ^{C1,C4,C5} [1.25]
Cluster 4 (n = 73)	1193 ^{C2,C5} [5975]	16.03* [14.33]	1011.04* [24.63]	50.83 ^{C1,C2,C5} [34]	6.40* [6.44]	0 ^{C2,C3,C5,C6} [0.95]
Cluster 5 (n = 67)	739 ^{C1,C3,C4,C6} [3154]	14.15 ^{C1,C3,C4} [12.94]	1015 ^{C1,C2,C4,C6} [24.71]	78.13* [26.03]	3.04 ^{C2,C3,C4,C6} [7.11]	0.12* [4.58]
Cluster 6 (n = 53)	1102 ^{C2,C5} [3512]	14.35 ^{C1,C2,C3,C4} [12.28]	1019.67* [17.92]	52.71 ^{C1,C2,C5} [29.25]	3.49 ^{C2,C4,C5} [2.96]	0 ^{C1,C4,C5} [0.21]

Notes: Data are expressed as median (interquartile range).

* Significant differences among clusters. C1 indicates significant differences from Cluster 1. C2 indicates significant differences from Cluster 2. C3 indicates significant differences from Cluster 3. C4 indicates significant differences from Cluster 4. C5 indicates significant differences from Cluster 5. C6 indicates significant differences from Cluster 6.

Table 4
Number and percentage of rainy days in each cluster.

	Total number of days		Rain days	
	n	%	n	%
Cluster 1	52	40.38	21	40.38
Cluster 2	98	19.39	19	19.39
Cluster 3	52	17.31	9	17.31
Cluster 4	73	43.84	32	43.84
Cluster 5	67	77.61	52	77.61
Cluster 6	53	11.32	6	11.32
Total	395	35.19	139	35.19

days associated with reduced BSS usage for active commuting were characterized by a temperature below 14.2 °C, relative humidity > 73 %, and abundant precipitation.

Based on these results, weather conditions appear to influence students' commutes differently than the general population's trips, a finding also reported in previous studies (Villarrasa-Sapiña et al., 2023). Further studies are needed to understand the origin of this difference (e. g., the level of humidity at which BSS use starts declining) and implement BSS promotion policies more accurately. This could clarify whether the effects of meteorological conditions observed in the present study is due to the age of the sample, type of trip, or both. In addition, further in-depth studies on BSS use by young students are needed to facilitate the development of appropriate policies to encourage active transportation among young students.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Israel Villarrasa-Sapiña: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sergio Montalt-García:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Xavier García-Massó:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Luis-Millán González-Moreno:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability statement

The authors declare the availability of the data by on request from the authors.

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